

Parameterized Complexity of Caching in Networks*

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Abstract

The fundamental caching problem in networks asks to find an allocation of contents to a network of caches with the aim of maximizing the cache hit rate. Despite the problem’s importance to a variety of research areas—including not only content delivery, but also edge intelligence and inference—and the extensive body of work on empirical aspects of caching, very little is known about the exact boundaries of tractability for the problem beyond its general NP-hardness. We close this gap by performing a comprehensive complexity-theoretic analysis of the problem through the lens of the parameterized complexity paradigm, which is designed to provide more precise statements regarding algorithmic tractability than classical complexity. Our results include algorithmic lower and upper bounds which together establish the conditions under which the caching problem becomes tractable.

1 Introduction

Caching is one of the most important tasks that need to be handled by modern-day content delivery networks (CDNs), and its role is expected to grow even further in the future, e.g., in the context of wireless communications (Liu et al., 2016; Paschos et al., 2018) and artificial intelligence. For the latter, it is crucial to cache: trained models for inference requests (Salem et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2024), information that can accelerate the training of large models (Lindgren et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2024), and trained model parts in distributed learning paradigms (Thapa et al., 2022; Tirana et al., 2024). Typically, in a caching network, one needs to decide where to store the contents in order to maximize metrics related to, e.g., network performance or user experience, with cache hit rate being the most predominant one (Paschos et al., 2020). While many recent works have investigated dynamic caching policies that either decide on caching before time-slotted requests or via the evic-

tion policy (Paschos et al., 2019; Bhattacharjee et al., 2020; Rohatgi, 2020; Paria and Sinha, 2021; Mhaisen et al., 2022), in this article we focus on proactive caching, which decides how to fill the caches based on anticipated requests. Proactive caching is of crucial importance in edge caching (Bastug et al., 2014; Tadrous and Eryilmaz, 2015) and is applied in contemporary caching architectures like Netflix’s CDN (Netflix, 2024b). In practice, content requests in video streaming services can be steered through trends or recommendation systems, leading to accurate predictions on the content popularity (Zhou et al., 2010; Netflix Tech Blog, 2016).

In the proactive setting, the caching problem in a network of caches (with possibly overlapping coverage) can be naturally represented as a bipartite graph between the set of users and the network of caches (of limited capacities), a set of contents, and information on the users’ anticipated requests; the task is to allocate the contents to caches to maximize the cache hit rate. This problem was proven to be NP-hard in the seminal work that formalized this setting (Shanmugam et al., 2013). The subsequent numerous variants of this base problem (Poularakis et al., 2014b; Dehghan et al., 2016; Krolkowski et al., 2018; Ricardo et al., 2021; Tsigkari and Spyropoulos, 2022) were all shown to be NP-hard by a reduction from it.

In the above works, the theoretical intractability was typically overcome via the use of heuristics or approximation algorithms. In fact, despite the extensive body of work on the caching problem, our understanding of its foundational complexity-theoretic aspects is still in its infancy. Specifically, very little is known about the problem’s “boundaries of tractability”, i.e., the precise conditions under which it becomes tractable. This gap is in stark contrast with recent substantial advances made in this direction for problems arising in artificial intelligence and machine learning such as Bayesian network learning (Ordyniak and Szeider, 2013; Ganian and Korchemna, 2021; Grüttemeier and Komusiewicz, 2022), data completion (Ganian et al., 2018, 2020; Eiben et al., 2021), and resource allocation (Bliem et al., 2016; Deligkas et al., 2021; Eiben et al., 2023).

The aim of this article is to close the aforementioned gap

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by carrying out a comprehensive study of the complexity-theoretic aspects of caching in its modern network-based formalization through the lens of *parameterized complexity* (Downey and Fellows, 2013; Cygan et al., 2015), which provides more refined tools to identify the conditions under which an NP-hard problem becomes tractable when compared to classical complexity. In the parameterized setting, the running times of algorithms are studied with respect to the input size n , but also an integer parameter k , which intuitively captures well-defined structural properties of the input. The most desirable outcome here is *fixed-parameter tractability* (FPT), which means that the problem can be solved in time $f(k) \cdot n^{O(1)}$ for a computable function f . A weaker notion of this is XP-tractability, which means that the problem can be solved in time $n^{f(k)}$. The least favorable outcome is paraNP-hardness, which means that the problem remains NP-hard even when k is a constant. Lastly, excluding fixed-parameter tractability is done by proving the problem is $W[1]$ -hard via a parameterized reduction.

Our Contributions. We consider three fundamental variants of the NETWORK-CACHING problem, which differ solely on the modeling and encoding of the content sizes. The main challenges of our investigation arise from the various aspects of the problem: when solving an instance one needs to (1) adhere to (knapsack-like) capacity constraints while (2) taking into account the graph structure of the caching network, and also (3) deal with the large variety of naturally occurring parameterizations. In particular, we study the complexity of these variants with respect to six parameters: the number C of caches, the maximum capacity K of any cache, the number S of contents, the number U of users, the maximum degree Δ of the network, and the maximum number λ of contents that any user may request.¹

We first consider the most computationally challenging variant of the problem, where the content and cache sizes are encoded in their “exact form” (as binary-encoded numbers). Interestingly, the inherent hardness of this variant—denoted HETNC-B—makes it easier to perform a detailed analysis compared to the two other variants. Note that the parameter K is incompatible with this model (bounding the cache capacities translates the problem to the unary-encoded setting investigated later). We begin by establishing the problem is FPT under the combined parameterizations² of $C+S$ (Theorem 1) and $U+S$ (or the complexity-theoretically equivalent $U+\lambda$) (Corollary 2); as HETNC-B is the most general of the three models, these tractability results carry over to the other two. Then, we show that HETNC-B is paraNP-hard under all remaining parameterizations (Theorems 7 and 10

¹The problem definitions and motivation for the employed parameterizations are deferred to Section 2.

²Parameterizing by a set of parameters is equivalent to parameterizing by their sum (Cygan et al., 2015).

Figure 1: Complexity landscapes of HETNC-B (top), HETNC-U (middle), and HOMNC (bottom). We (mostly) omit parameterizations including $C + \Delta$, $U + \Delta$, $U + \lambda$, or $S + \lambda$, as the first two, the third, and the last are complexity-theoretically equivalent to $C + U$, $U + S$, and S , respectively. Indeed, for any pair of combined parameters claimed to be equivalent, each of them can be bounded by a computable function of the other. To prove the first two equivalences, note that $\Delta \leq C + U$, $U \leq C \cdot \Delta$, and $C \leq U \cdot \Delta$. For the latter two, note that $S \leq U \cdot \lambda$ and $\lambda \leq S$.

and Corollary 11). The clean cut between tractability and intractability for HETNC-B is depicted in Fig. 1 (top).

Next, we consider the unary variant of the problem, where one still distinguishes between contents of different sizes, but only on a more categorical scale (e.g., by distinguishing between full movies, longer shows, and shorter shows in the setting of video streaming). Here, the sizes of the contents are encoded in unary, which affects the complexity of the associated HETNC-U problem. On the positive side, in addition to $C+S$ and $U+S$, we identify a third fixed-parameter tractable fragment of the problem, specifically $C+K$ (Theorem 3). Moreover, we obtain XP-tractability for HETNC-U with respect to C alone (Theorem 3), and complement this result by establishing $W[1]$ -hardness (and hence, ruling out fixed-parameter tractability) even when combining C with either U or λ (Theorem 8 and Corollary 9). All fragments not covered by these cases are then paraNP-hard (Theorems 7 and 8), except for $U+K$ for which we establish XP-tractability (Theorem 4). The obtained complexity landscape of HETNC-U is illustrated in Fig. 1 (middle).

Finally, we turn to the simplest, totally uniform case where each content has the same size; we denote the associated problem HOMNC. We first demonstrate the challenging nature of even this variant by strengthening the previously known lower bound (Shanmugam et al., 2013) and establish-

ing NP-hardness when $S = \lambda = 2$, $K = 1$, and, additionally, $\Delta = 3$ (Theorem 7). Furthermore, unlike for HETNC-U, here we establish XP-tractability with respect to \mathcal{U} alone (Corollary 6). For the lower bounds, all paraNP-hardness results, other than with respect to \mathcal{U} alone, can be shown to carry over to the simpler setting of HOMNC. Our results for HOMNC are displayed in Fig. 1 (bottom).

To complete the complexity landscapes for HETNC-U and HOMNC, it remains to complement some of the obtained XP algorithms (those depicted in blue in Fig. 1) with $W[1]$ -hardness results to exclude fixed-parameter tractability. In this respect, we show that resolving any of the open cases for HOMNC by establishing $W[1]$ -hardness (which we conjecture to hold) immediately implies the $W[1]$ -hardness of all the open cases depicted in Fig. 1. In fact, we show that all 5 “open” parameterizations for HOMNC are complexity-theoretically equivalent to each other (Theorem 14). Hence, while settling these 5 open questions seems to require novel ideas and techniques beyond today’s state of the art, resolving any of them settles the complexity of the others.

As our final contribution, we complement the complexity-theoretic landscapes depicted in Fig. 1 by considering whether tractability can be achieved by exploiting finer structural properties of the network. Indeed, for graph-theoretic problems, it is typical to also consider structural parameterizations of the input graph such as their *treewidth* (Robertson and Seymour, 1986), *treedepth* (Nesetril and de Mendez, 2012), *feedback edge number* (Ganian and Korchemna, 2021; Bredereck et al., 2022), or *vertex cover number* (Bodlaender et al., 2023; Chalopin et al., 2024). It is also common to study such problems when the graph is restricted to being *planar*, i.e., it can be drawn on a plane such that none of its edges cross. This is particularly important for NETWORK-CACHING, as planar networks will have much less overlapping cache coverage. As our last set of results, we classify the complexity of HETNC-B, HETNC-U, and HOMNC with respect to the above structural restrictions; in particular, we show that almost none of these restrictions help achieve tractability, even when combined with those considered in Fig. 1.

2 Setup and Problem Definitions

We use standard graph-theoretic terminology (Diestel, 2012). For any positive integer n , let $[n] = \{1, \dots, n\}$. We consider a set \mathcal{C} of $C := |\mathcal{C}|$ caches and a set \mathcal{U} of $U := |\mathcal{U}|$ users, each of which has access to a subset of caches (which could be determined by, e.g., routing or other network policies). This naturally defines a bipartite graph $G = (\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E})$, where \mathcal{E} are the edges between the two independent sets \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{U} , as depicted in Fig. 2. This is the predominant setting in the literature (Shanmugam et al., 2013; Paria and Sinha,

Figure 2: Illustration of a bipartite graph between users and subsets of the caches in our setting.

2021; Mhaisen et al., 2022; Tsigkari and Spyropoulos, 2022; Salem et al., 2023). For all $u \in \mathcal{U}$, the subset of caches that u has access to is the neighborhood of u , denoted by $N(u)$. For all $c \in \mathcal{C}$, the subset of users that c serves is $N(c)$. The maximum degree of the network is $\Delta := \max_{v \in V(G)} |N(v)|$. The users have access to a catalog \mathcal{S} of $S := |\mathcal{S}|$ contents, where the size of a content $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is denoted by $\sigma(s)$; as is common in the literature (Shanmugam et al., 2013; Blaszczyszyn and Giovanidis, 2015; Paschos et al., 2019) and, without loss of generality, the content sizes are positive integers. In our analysis, we consider both the cases of contents of equal (homogeneous) and of variable (heterogeneous) sizes, where the former is equivalent to rescaling and fixing $\sigma(s) = 1$ for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$.

For each cache $c \in \mathcal{C}$, we denote by $\kappa(c) \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ its capacity, and we denote the maximum capacity of a cache (over all caches) by $K := \max_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \kappa(c)$. As a cache with capacity equal to $\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sigma(s)$ can store all the contents in \mathcal{S} , without loss of generality, we assume that $K \leq \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sigma(s)$, which, in the case of HOMNC, implies that $K \leq S$. However, in real systems, K is far from this upper bound. Indeed, in the case of Netflix, the cache capacity may be as little as 0.3% of the catalog size (Paschos et al., 2016; Netflix, 2024a).

A user requests contents following a probability distribution. Specifically, a user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ requests content $s \in \mathcal{S}$ with probability $p_{us} \in [0, 1]$, such that $\sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} p_{us} = 1$ for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$. The values p_{us} are considered to be known and represented as rational numbers; these may be based on past user requests, trending contents, etc. We denote by λ the maximum number of contents any user may request, i.e., $\lambda := \max_{u \in \mathcal{U}} |\{s \in \mathcal{S} \mid p_{us} > 0\}|$. A request for content s by user u is served by a cache adjacent to user u where the requested content is stored. If the content is not stored in any of the adjacent caches, then the request is served by a large cache outside of \mathcal{C} containing all contents; this will induce traffic at the backhaul network with a potential impact on user quality and retrieval costs (Shanmugam et al., 2013; Poularakis et al., 2014a). Thus, it is important to optimize the caching allocation in the “smaller” caches in proximity of the users; these are updated during off-peak hours (Netflix, 2024b) and the cache placement is static between two updates. Moreover, each user $u \in \mathcal{U}$ is characterized by a

priority weight $w(u) \in \mathbb{Q}^+$ that may, e.g., capture the guarantee of high quality of service (QoS) for premium users in streaming platforms (Disney+, 2023; Netflix, 2023).

Let a *caching allocation* $Z : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow 2^{\mathcal{S}}$ be a mapping that assigns a subset of contents to each cache. If Z complies with the size constraints of the individual caches, i.e., $\forall c \in \mathcal{C} : \sum_{s \in Z(c)} \sigma(s) \leq \kappa(c)$, then it is *feasible*. For a user $u \in \mathcal{U}$, the set of contents stored in its adjacent small caches (i.e., in $N(u)$) under a caching allocation Z is defined as the set $H(u) := \{s \in \mathcal{S} \mid \exists c \in N(u) : s \in Z(c)\}$. Potential requests for contents in $H(u)$ will induce cache hits. We can now define the *cache hit rate* (Shanmugam et al., 2013; Paschos et al., 2020) achieved by a caching allocation Z to be $CH(Z) := \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \sum_{s \in H(u)} w(u) \cdot p_{us}$.

As is common in complexity-theoretic studies, we consider the decision variant of the problem in question; we note that all of our algorithms can also solve the corresponding optimization problem and are constructive, i.e., they can output the optimal feasible caching allocation. We can now define the problem archetype studied in this paper.

NETWORK-CACHING

Input: A bipartite graph $G = (\mathcal{C}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{E})$, the cache capacities $\kappa(c_1), \dots, \kappa(c_C)$, a set \mathcal{S} of contents of sizes $\sigma(s_1), \dots, \sigma(s_S)$, the request probabilities p_{us} for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$ and $s \in \mathcal{S}$, the user weights $w(u)$ for all $u \in \mathcal{U}$, and $\ell \in \mathbb{Q}^+$.

Question: Is there a feasible caching allocation Z such that $CH(Z) \geq \ell$?

As the complexity of NETWORK-CACHING depends on how the sizes of contents are encoded and represented, we distinguish between the following three variants of it:

- In **HOMOGENEOUS NETWORK-CACHING (HOMNC)**, the sizes of the contents are the same, and thus, without loss of generality, are equal to 1, i.e., $\sigma(s_1) = \dots = \sigma(s_S) = 1$. This restriction has been considered in past works (Błaszczyszyn and Giovanidis, 2015; Paschos et al., 2019), and can be justified on the basis that contents could in practice be partitioned into equal-sized chunks and cached independently, see (Maggi et al., 2018).
- In **HETEROGENEOUS NETWORK-CACHING (UNARY) (HETNC-U)**, the numbers $\sigma(s_1), \dots, \sigma(s_S)$ are encoded in unary. For our complexity-theoretic analysis, this is equivalent to assuming that the sizes of contents are not much larger than the input size. HETNC captures the situation where we do not represent the sizes of contents by their exact bit size, but rather by a rough categorical scale. As an example from the video-on-demand setting, movies are typically roughly twice as

long as 1-hour shows, which are then roughly twice as long as 30-minute shows, and hence, we can represent the sizes of these items by the integers 4, 2, and 1, respectively.

- In **HETEROGENEOUS NETWORK-CACHING (BINARY) (HETNC-B)**, the numbers $\sigma(s_1), \dots, \sigma(s_S)$ are encoded in binary, meaning that they can be exponentially larger than the input size. This situation may arise, e.g., if one were to simply use the exact sizes of contents.

As mentioned earlier, we study three fundamental variants of NETWORK-CACHING with respect to all combinations of the parameterizations discussed in Section 1. As C , K , S , and U are all natural input parameters of this problem, it is only logical to consider parameterizations by them. On the other hand, we also consider the auxiliary parameters Δ and λ , as one could naturally think that this could lead to tractability. Indeed, if each user only has access to a bounded number of caches and, additionally, each cache only serves a bounded number of users, then, intuitively, this should render the problem significantly easier. Further, if each user only requests (with non-zero probability) a bounded number of contents, then, instinctively, this should also simplify the problem. However, as our first lower bound result (Theorem 7), we surprisingly show that this is not the case.

3 Establishing Upper Bounds: Algorithms

In this section, we provide all the tractability results delimiting the boundaries of tractability depicted in Fig. 1, i.e., algorithms. We first analyze HETNC-B, as any tractability results for this problem also carry over to the other two. We use a direct branching argument to show:

Theorem 1. HETNC-B is FPT parameterized by $C + S$.

Proof. We apply a brute-force algorithm that computes all the possible caching allocations and finds a feasible one with the largest cache hit rate. For each cache, it branches over the 2^S possibilities of storing contents in that cache. Thus, there are $\mathcal{O}(2^{SC})$ possible caching allocations. For each caching allocation, it takes $\mathcal{O}(C \cdot S)$ time to test if it is feasible and $\mathcal{O}(U \cdot C \cdot S)$ time to compute its cache hit rate. Thus, the algorithm's total runtime is $\mathcal{O}(2^{SC} \cdot C \cdot S \cdot U)$. Its correctness follows since it enumerates all caching allocations. \square

With Theorem 1 in hand, we can provide a second fixed-parameter tractable fragment for HETNC-B.

Corollary 2. HETNC-B is FPT parameterized by $U + S$.

Proof. We apply a simple preprocessing procedure where, for each set of $S + 1$ or more caches with the same neighborhood in G (i.e., which are accessible by precisely the same set of users), we keep the S caches with the largest capacities and delete the rest. We call the resulting graph G' . Note that it takes $\mathcal{O}(C \cdot \log(C) \cdot U)$ time to construct G' from G .

To see that (G, ℓ) is a yes-instance if and only if (G', ℓ) is a yes-instance, for any set of caches with the same neighborhood in G , it suffices to note that, as there are only S contents, at most S of these caches can contain a distinct content stored in them that is not stored in any of the other caches in this set. Thus, for any such set of caches, since only the caches with the smallest capacities are deleted, then any set of contents that can be stored prior to deleting these caches, can also be stored after deleting these caches.

Since there are 2^U different subsets of \mathcal{U} , there are at most $2^U \cdot S$ caches in G' . At this point, it suffices to apply the brute force algorithm from Theorem 1 on G' . Thus, the total runtime of this algorithm (including constructing G' from G) is $\mathcal{O}(C \cdot \log(C) \cdot U + 2^{S \cdot (2^U \cdot S)} \cdot 2^U \cdot S \cdot S \cdot U) = \mathcal{O}(C \cdot \log(C) \cdot U + 2^{S^2 \cdot 2^U + U} \cdot S^2 \cdot U)$, and the correctness follows immediately from the argument provided in the previous paragraph. \square

We now have all the tractability results needed for Fig. 1 (top). For HETNC-U, we contrast the situation for the binary case by designing a dynamic programming algorithm whose running time is XP when parameterized by C alone, and even FPT when parameterized by $C + K$.

Theorem 3. HETNC-U is XP parameterized by C and FPT parameterized by $C + K$.

Proof. Let c_1, \dots, c_C be the caches and s_1, \dots, s_S the contents of the catalog. Let A be a C -dimensional array where, for all $i \in [C]$, the i^{th} dimension of the array has size $\kappa(c_i) + 1$. We use a zero-based indexing for A , that is, the indices start from 0. Essentially, each entry in A will correspond to the best possible cache hit rate that can be achieved when the caches have the remaining capacities corresponding to the coordinates of the entry, with the value of the i^{th} coordinate corresponding to the remaining capacity of the cache c_i for all $i \in [C]$. Initially, we set all of the entries of A to -1 except for one entry that we set to 0, whose coordinates correspond to all of the caches having their full capacities remaining (i.e., $A[\kappa(c_1)] \dots [\kappa(c_C)] = 0$). The idea here is that -1 is a placeholder that represents that a caching allocation resulting in the represented cache capacities cannot yet exist, which is indeed the case here since the capacities of the caches cannot be reduced without storing contents in them. Then, we will update the entries of A through a dynamic programming approach considering the contents one by one and all the possibilities of adding the content to the caches. In order to perform this update properly, we will also

have a second array A' with $A' = A$ initially. The algorithm proceeds as follows.

For $i = 1$ to $i = S$, do the following. For each non-negative entry $A[j_1] \dots [j_C]$ in A and each of the 2^C subsets $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \mathcal{C}$, possibly update the entries of A' as follows. Let $CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i)$ be the cache hits obtained only from storing s_i in the caches of \mathcal{C}' . For all $t \in [C]$, let $q_t = 1$ if $c_t \in \mathcal{C}'$, and otherwise, let $q_t = 0$. If, for all $t \in [C]$, it holds that $j_t - (q_t \cdot \sigma(s_i)) \geq 0$, and

$$A[j_1] \dots [j_C] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i) >$$

$$A'[j_1 - (q_1 \cdot \sigma(s_i)) \dots [j_C - (q_C \cdot \sigma(s_i))],$$

then set

$$A'[j_1 - (q_1 \cdot \sigma(s_i)) \dots [j_C - (q_C \cdot \sigma(s_i))] =$$

$$A[j_1] \dots [j_C] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i).$$

This ends the two innermost For loops. Before incrementing i by 1, set $A = A'$.

Once the above algorithm is finished, let ℓ' be the largest entry in A' . Note that ℓ' corresponds to the maximum cache hit rate possible among all feasible caching allocations. Hence, if $\ell' \geq \ell$, then return that this is a yes-instance, and otherwise, return that this is a no-instance.

Now, we prove the correctness of the algorithm by induction on the number i of contents processed. For the base case, $i = 0$ and all the entries in A' are -1 except for $A'[\kappa(c_1)] \dots [\kappa(c_C)]$ which is 0, and this is correct since it is not possible to have reduced cache capacities nor to have a positive cache hit rate without storing any contents in caches. Trivially, all of the possible ways (in fact, the only way) of storing zero contents have been considered. For the inductive hypothesis, suppose for some $0 \leq i < S$ that after the i^{th} iteration of the outermost For loop has completed (before the first iteration of the outermost For loop has begun in the case $i = 0$), each entry in A' is correct and every possible feasible caching allocation for the first i contents have been considered thus far. Specifically, in this case we say that an entry in A' is correct if (1) it is -1 if it is not possible to achieve the remaining cache capacities by only storing contents from the first i contents or (2) it is the maximum possible value of the cache hit rate that can be achieved by a feasible caching allocation for the first i contents such that the remaining capacities of the caches correspond to the coordinates of the entry in A' .

We now prove the inductive step for $i + 1$. In the $(i + 1)^{\text{th}}$ iteration of the outermost For loop of the algorithm, initially $A = A'$. Then, for each non-negative entry $A[j_1] \dots [j_C]$ in A , all of the possible ways of caching the content s_{i+1} in the caches whose remaining capacities correspond to the coordinates of $A[j_1] \dots [j_C]$ are considered. This covers all the possible feasible caching allocations for the first $i + 1$

contents since, by the inductive hypothesis, all of the entries in A are correct, and thus, the non-negative entries in A should not be considered as they correspond to remaining cache capacities that are unattainable by storing contents from the first i contents. Now, the only entries in A' that can be updated from considering $A[j_1] \dots [j_C]$ are correctly those whose coordinates are attainable from $A[j_1] \dots [j_C]$ by storing the content s_{i+1} in a subset of the caches for all such subsets that do not result in negative coordinates. For a subset $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \mathcal{C}$ of the caches, the corresponding entry in A' is only updated if the current value of that entry in A' is less than $A[j_1] \dots [j_C] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_{i+1})$. We now argue that this update step is correct. First, if the above condition is not met, then the entry in A' should not be updated. Indeed, by the inductive hypothesis, there exists a feasible caching allocation of the first i contents that achieves at least as large a cache hit rate as the one that would be obtained from $A[j_1] \dots [j_C]$ and \mathcal{C}' , and they both have the same remaining cache capacities. Second, if the above condition is met, then the entry in A' should be updated. Indeed, by the inductive hypothesis, there exists a feasible caching allocation for the first i contents whose cache hit rate is $A[j_1] \dots [j_C]$ and whose remaining cache capacities for the caches c_1, \dots, c_C are j_1, \dots, j_C , respectively. Thus, there also exists a feasible caching allocation for which the remaining cache capacities correspond to the coordinates of the entry of A' being updated, and whose cache hit rate is $A[j_1] \dots [j_C] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_{i+1})$ by the definition of $CH(\mathcal{C}', s_{i+1})$. Hence, all of the entries of A' are correct after the $(i+1)$ th iteration of the outermost For loop has completed, and thus, we have proven the inductive step. It is then clear that ℓ' corresponds to the maximum cache hit rate possible among all feasible caching allocations, and so, the algorithm decides correctly on whether or not it is a yes-or-no-instance of the problem.

Finally, we prove the runtime of the algorithm. For each $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \mathcal{C}$ and $i \in [S]$, it takes $\mathcal{O}(C \cdot U)$ time to compute $CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i)$ and to check whether, for all $t \in [C]$, $j_t - (q_t \cdot \sigma(s_i)) \geq 0$. Since the largest cache hit rate of any of the entries in A' can be stored and updated in the last iteration of the outermost For loop, ℓ' can be extracted from A' in $\mathcal{O}(1)$ time. Thus, for any $i \in [S]$, the total runtime for the i th iteration of the outermost For loop of the algorithm takes $\mathcal{O}((K+1)^C \cdot 2^C \cdot C \cdot U)$ time. As there are S such iterations of this For loop, the total runtime of the algorithm is $\mathcal{O}((K+1)^C \cdot 2^C \cdot C \cdot U \cdot S)$. \square

The ideas from the above algorithm can be extended to show that HETNC-U is XP parameterized by $U + K$. This is done by grouping caches together into types based on the users they serve and their capacities, and keeping track of the number of caches of each type that are left as we fill them.

Theorem 4. HETNC-U is XP parameterized by $U + K$.

Proof. Let s_1, \dots, s_S be the contents of the catalog. Also, let $\mathcal{U}_1, \dots, \mathcal{U}_{2^U}$ be the distinct subsets of \mathcal{U} and, for all $r \in [2^U]$, let $\mathcal{C}_r := \{c \mid N(c) = \mathcal{U}_r \text{ and } c \in \mathcal{C}\}$. Further, for all integers $0 \leq y \leq [K]$, let \mathcal{C}_r^y be the set of caches in \mathcal{C}_r whose remaining capacities (after possibly storing some contents) are equal to y . Thus, there are $T := 2^U \cdot (K+1)$ sets of the form \mathcal{C}_r^y or, in other words, types of caches. Let A be a T -dimensional array where, for all $i \in [T]$, the i th dimension of the array corresponds to a cache type and has size $C+1$. Specifically, for all $r \in [2^U]$ and integers $0 \leq y \leq K$, the cache of type \mathcal{C}_r^y corresponds to the $((r-1) \cdot (K+1) + y + 1)$ th dimension of A , and this dimension's coordinate corresponds to the number of caches of type \mathcal{C}_r^y remaining. We use a zero-based indexing for A , that is, the indices start from 0. Essentially, each entry in A will correspond to the best possible cache hit rate that can be achieved when the numbers of each type of cache remaining correspond to the coordinates of the entry. Initially, we set all of the entries of A to -1 except for one entry that we set to 0, whose coordinates correspond to the initial numbers of each type of cache before any contents are stored in caches. The -1 is a placeholder and plays an analogous role as in the proof of Theorem 3. Then, we will update the entries of A through a dynamic programming approach considering the contents one by one and all the possibilities of adding the content to types of caches. In order to do this update properly, we will also have a second array A' with $A' = A$ initially. The algorithm proceeds as follows.

For $i = 1$ to $i = S$, do the following. For each non-negative entry $A[j_1] \dots [j_T]$ in A and each of the 2^T subsets of $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \{\mathcal{C}_r^y \mid r \in [2^U] \text{ and } 0 \leq y \leq K\}$, possibly update the entries of A' as follows. Let $CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i)$ be the cache hits obtained only from storing s_i in the types of caches of \mathcal{C}' . When storing s_i in the types of caches of \mathcal{C}' , this changes the number of certain types of caches remaining, possibly increasing or decreasing it for some. To simplify matters, without loss of generality, from j_1, \dots, j_T , after storing the content s_i in the types of caches of \mathcal{C}' , let j'_1, \dots, j'_T be the resulting numbers of each cache type remaining. If, for all $t \in [T]$, it holds that $j'_t \geq 0$, and

$$A[j_1] \dots [j_T] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i) > A'[j'_1] \dots [j'_T],$$

then set

$$A'[j'_1] \dots [j'_T] = A[j_1] \dots [j_T] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i).$$

This ends the two innermost For loops. Before incrementing i by 1, set $A = A'$.

Once the above algorithm is finished, let ℓ' be the largest entry in A' and note that ℓ' corresponds to the maximum cache hit rate possible among all feasible caching allocations. Hence, if $\ell' \geq \ell$, then return that this is a yes-instance, and otherwise, return that this is a no-instance.

Now, we prove the correctness of the algorithm by induction on the number i of contents processed. For the base case, $i = 0$ and all the entries in A' are -1 except for one which is 0 , whose coordinates correspond to the initial numbers of each type of cache before any contents are stored in caches, and this is correct since it is not possible to have reduced cache capacities nor to have a positive cache hit rate without storing any contents in caches. Trivially, all of the possible ways (in fact, the only way) of storing zero contents have been considered. For the inductive hypothesis, suppose for some $0 \leq i < S$ that after the i^{th} iteration of the outermost For loop has completed (before the first iteration of the outermost For loop has begun in the case $i = 0$), each entry in A' is correct and every possible feasible caching allocation for the first i contents have been considered thus far. Specifically, in this case we say that an entry in A' is correct if (1) it is -1 if it is not possible to achieve the remaining numbers of each cache type by only storing contents from the first i contents or (2) it is the maximum possible value of the cache hit rate that can be achieved by a feasible caching allocation for the first i contents such that the remaining numbers of each cache type correspond to the coordinates of the entry in A' .

We now prove the inductive step for $i + 1$. In the $(i + 1)^{\text{th}}$ iteration of the outermost For loop of the algorithm, initially $A = A'$. Then, for each non-negative entry $A[j_1] \dots [j_T]$ in A , all of the possible ways of caching the content s_{i+1} in types of caches whose remaining numbers correspond to the coordinates of $A[j_1] \dots [j_T]$ are considered. This covers all the possible feasible caching allocations for the first $i + 1$ contents since, by the inductive hypothesis, all of the entries in A are correct, and thus, the non-negative entries in A should not be considered as they correspond to remaining numbers of cache types that are unattainable by storing contents from the first i contents. Also, it should be noted that the previous statement is true since there is no sense in storing the same content in two or more caches of the same type as they serve the same subset of the users. Now, the only entries in A' that can be updated from considering $A[j_1] \dots [j_T]$ are correctly those whose coordinates are attainable from $A[j_1] \dots [j_T]$ by storing the content s_{i+1} in a subset of the cache types for all such subsets that do not result in negative coordinates. For a subset $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \{\mathcal{C}_r^y \mid r \in [2^U] \text{ and } 0 \leq y \leq K\}$ of the cache types, the corresponding entry in A' is only updated if the current value of that entry in A' is less than $A[j_1] \dots [j_T] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_{i+1})$. We now argue that this update step is correct. First, if the above condition is not met, then the entry in A' should not be updated. Indeed, by the inductive hypothesis, there exists a feasible caching allocation of the first i contents that achieves at least as large a cache hit rate as the one that would be obtained from $A[j_1] \dots [j_T]$ and \mathcal{C}' , and they both have the same remaining numbers of cache types. Second, if the above condition is met, then the entry

in A' should be updated. Indeed, by the inductive hypothesis, there exists a feasible caching allocation for the first i contents whose cache hit rate is $A[j_1] \dots [j_T]$ and whose remaining numbers of cache types are j_1, \dots, j_T , in that order. Thus, there also exists a feasible caching allocation for which the remaining numbers of cache types correspond to the coordinates of the entry of A' being updated, and whose cache hit rate is $A[j_1] \dots [j_T] + CH(\mathcal{C}', s_{i+1})$ by the definition of $CH(\mathcal{C}', s_{i+1})$. Hence, all of the entries of A' are correct after the $(i + 1)^{\text{th}}$ iteration of the outermost For loop has completed, and thus, we have proven the inductive step. It is then clear that ℓ' corresponds to the maximum cache hit rate possible among all feasible caching allocations, and so, the algorithm decides correctly on whether or not it is a yes-or-no-instance of the problem.

Finally, we prove the runtime of the algorithm. As in the proof of Theorem 3, for each $\mathcal{C}' \subseteq \{\mathcal{C}_r^y \mid r \in [2^U] \text{ and } 0 \leq y \leq K\}$ and $i \in [S]$, it takes $\mathcal{O}(C \cdot U)$ time to compute $CH(\mathcal{C}', s_i)$. It takes $\mathcal{O}(T)$ time to check whether $j'_t \geq 0$ for each $t \in [T]$. Also as in the proof of Theorem 3, at the end ℓ' can be extracted from A' in $\mathcal{O}(1)$ time. Thus, for any $i \in [S]$, the total runtime for the i^{th} iteration of the outermost For loop of the algorithm takes $\mathcal{O}((C+1)^T \cdot 2^T \cdot (C \cdot U + T))$ time. As there are S such iterations of this For loop, the total runtime of the algorithm is $\mathcal{O}((C+1)^T \cdot 2^T \cdot (C \cdot U + T) \cdot S) = \mathcal{O}((C+1)^{f(U,K)} \cdot S)$ for some computable function f . \square

We now have all the tractability results we need to establish Fig. 1 (middle): the upper bounds follow from Theorems 1, 3, and 4 plus Corollary 2. Finally, we establish that HOMNC is XP parameterized by U through the following observation that allows us to bound the number of caches by a function of the number of users, after which the XP algorithm provided in Theorem 3 can be applied. The reason why this only works for HOMNC is that it amalgamates caches with the same neighborhood into a single cache with a larger capacity, which cannot be safely done (i.e., without changing the outcome of the problem) in the other settings due to the variable content sizes.

Observation 5. *Any instance (G, ℓ) of HOMNC with U users can be reduced in polynomial time to an equivalent instance (G', ℓ) of HOMNC with at most 2^U caches.*

Proof. To obtain G' from G , for each set of 2 or more caches with the same neighborhood in G , delete all the caches except for one, and give this cache a capacity equal to the sum of all the capacities of these deleted caches plus its own original capacity. Since there are 2^U different subsets of the users in G , there are at most 2^U caches in G' . This reduction takes polynomial time and the equivalence of the two instances is immediate as all the contents have unit size. \square

Theorem 3 together with Observation 5 immediately yields the following corollary.

Corollary 6. HOMNC is XP parameterized by U .

Corollary 6 is the only additional tractability result needed for the landscape in Fig. 1 (bottom).

4 Establishing Lower Bounds: Hardness

In this section, we establish the lower bounds required for the landscapes depicted in Fig. 1. As we are proving hardness results, it is advantageous to first consider parameterizations of HOMNC as they will carry over to HETNC-U and HETNC-B. To simplify our exposition, we denote all of the instances constructed in our reductions as a bipartite graph G together with the target cache hit rate ℓ .

We first strengthen the known result (Shanmugam et al., 2013) that HOMNC is NP-hard even if $S = \lambda = 2$ and $K = 1$, by showing that the same holds even if additionally restricted to networks where $\Delta = 3$. We prove this via a reduction from the NP-hard MONOTONE NAE-3-SAT-B3 problem (Kratochvíl and Tuza, 2002), whose definition is as follows.

MONOTONE NAE-3-SAT-B3

Input: A 3-CNF formula ϕ in which each clause contains 2 or 3 literals, and every variable appears in at most 3 clauses and only in its positive form.

Question: Is there an NAE satisfying assignment for ϕ , i.e., a truth assignment to the variables appearing in ϕ such that each clause in ϕ contains both a variable set to True and a variable set to False?

Theorem 7. HOMNC is NP-hard, even if $S = \lambda = 2$, $K = 1$, and $\Delta = 3$.

Proof. We reduce from MONOTONE NAE-3-SAT-B3. Let x_1, \dots, x_n and C_1, \dots, C_m be the variables and clauses, respectively, of an input formula ϕ of MONOTONE NAE-3-SAT-B3. We construct an instance (G, ℓ) of HOMNC from the incidence graph³ G_ϕ of ϕ as follows. Each variable vertex x_i , $i \in [n]$, in G_ϕ corresponds to a cache c_{x_i} of capacity 1 in G . There are only two contents in the catalog: True and False. Each clause vertex C_j , $j \in [m]$, in G_ϕ corresponds to a user u_{C_j} (of weight 1) in G that requests True and False with equal probability. Thus, if a variable appears in a clause in ϕ , then the variable's corresponding cache is adjacent to

³The incidence graph, denoted by G_ϕ , is the bipartite graph obtained by creating a vertex for each variable and clause in ϕ , and adding an edge between a clause vertex and a variable vertex if and only if that variable is contained in that clause in ϕ .

the clause's corresponding user in G . Lastly, set $\ell := U$. This completes the construction of (G, ℓ) , which is clearly achieved in polynomial time. Further, it is easy to verify that, in (G, ℓ) , $S = 2$, $K = 1$, $\lambda = 2$, and $\Delta = 3$ (as each variable appears in at most 3 clauses in ϕ).

For the first direction, assume that there is an NAE satisfying assignment for ϕ . For each $i \in [n]$, if the NAE satisfying assignment for ϕ sets the variable x_i to True (False, resp.), then store the content True (False, resp.) in the cache c_{x_i} in G . The NAE satisfying assignment for ϕ ensures that each clause in ϕ contains a variable set to True and one set to False. Thus, this is a feasible caching allocation in G that ensures that each user is adjacent to a cache that stored True and one that stored False, and so, it achieves a cache hit rate of ℓ . Indeed, each clause in ϕ corresponds to a user in G that is adjacent to 2 or 3 caches that correspond to the 2 or 3 variables contained in that clause in ϕ .

For the other direction, assume that there is a feasible caching allocation in G achieving a cache hit rate of ℓ . This caching allocation ensures that each user u_{C_j} , $j \in [m]$, is adjacent to a cache that stored True and one that stored False. For each variable x_i , $i \in [n]$, in ϕ , set its truth value to the one that corresponds to the content stored in x_i 's corresponding cache c_{x_i} in G according to this caching allocation. Then, this truth assignment is an NAE satisfying assignment for ϕ since each clause contains a variable set to True and one set to False. Indeed, each user in G corresponds to a clause in ϕ that contains 2 or 3 variables corresponding to the 2 or 3 caches adjacent to that user in G . \square

Theorem 7 settles the complexity of our three problems with respect to all our considered parameters except for C and U . For these two parameters, the complexity differs depending on the problem and, as we showed in Section 3, HOMNC is XP parameterized by C or U . For HETNC-U, the three additional lower bound results we need to establish the landscape in Fig. 1 (middle) are W[1]-hardness with respect to $C + \lambda$ and $C + U$, and paraNP-hardness when parameterized by U alone. For the latter two lower bounds, we provide a simple reduction from UNARY BIN PACKING, which is not only NP-hard, but also W[1]-hard when parameterized by the number of bins (Jansen et al., 2013). Its definition is as follows.

UNARY BIN PACKING

Input: A set I of item sizes that are positive integers encoded in unary, and $b, B \in \mathbb{Z}^+$.

Question: Is there a partition of the items in I into b bins of capacity B ?

Theorem 8. HETNC-U is NP-hard and also W[1]-hard parameterized by C , even if $U = 1$.

Proof. We reduce from UNARY BIN PACKING. From an instance (I, b, B) of UNARY BIN PACKING, we construct an instance (G, ℓ) of HETNC-U as follows. There is a single user u (of weight 1) and b caches of capacity B that are all adjacent to u . For each item size in I , there is a content of the same size and the user u requests each of the $|I|$ contents with equal probability. Set $\ell := 1$. This completes the construction of (G, ℓ) , which is clearly achieved in polynomial time. Further, it is easy to verify that, in (G, ℓ) , $C = b$ and $U = 1$.

To establish correctness, it suffices to observe that our construction maintains a direct correspondence between storing a content in a cache (in the constructed instance of HETNC-U) and placing the corresponding item in the respective bin (in the original instance of UNARY BIN PACKING). Hence, a caching allocation achieves a cache hit rate of $\ell = 1$ if and only if the corresponding placement of items in bins represents a solution to the original UNARY BIN PACKING problem. \square

For the last lower bound in the unary case, a direct adaptation of the reduction used in Theorem 8 yields that HETNC-U is W[1]-hard parameterized by C when each user requests a single content.

Corollary 9. *HETNC-U is NP-hard and also W[1]-hard parameterized by C , even if $\lambda = 1$.*

Proof. Let $s_1, \dots, s_{|I|}$ be the contents requested with non-zero probability by the single user u in the reduction in the proof of Theorem 8 (recall that $|I|$ is the number of items in the input instance of UNARY BIN PACKING). We adapt that reduction as follows: instead of creating the single user u , for each $s \in s_1, \dots, s_{|I|}$, we create a separate user u_s of weight 1. Each such user u_s only requests the content s , specifically with probability $p_{u_s s} = 1$, and is moreover adjacent to every cache in the instance. Finally, we set $\ell := |I|$ instead of 1.

To establish correctness, we again observe that our construction maintains a direct correspondence between storing a content in a cache and placing the corresponding item in the respective bin. Hence, a caching allocation achieves a cache hit rate of $\ell = |I|$ if and only if the corresponding placement of items in bins represents a solution to the original UNARY BIN PACKING problem. \square

When the sizes of the contents are encoded in binary, one can establish a much stronger notion of intractability (paraNP-hardness) for HETNC when parameterized by C . Indeed, as was observed for other variants of NETWORK-CACHING (Poularakis et al., 2019), HETNC-B admits a trivial polynomial-time reduction from the weakly NP-hard 0-1 KNAPSACK problem (Garey and Johnson, 1979), whose definition is as follows.

0-1 KNAPSACK

Input: A knapsack of capacity $W \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, a set I of items numbered from 1 to n with weights $w_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and values $v_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ ($i \in [n]$), and $t \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, all encoded in binary.

Question: Is there a subset of the items that can be placed in the knapsack (i.e., their total weight does not exceed W) such that their total value is at least t ?

Theorem 10. *HETNC-B is NP-hard, even if $U = C = 1$.*

Proof. From an instance (W, I, t) of 0-1 KNAPSACK, we construct an instance (G, ℓ) of HETNC-B as follows. For each $i \in [n]$, there is a content s_i of size $\sigma(s_i) := w_i$ representing the item i of weight w_i from the 0-1 KNAPSACK instance. Further, there is one cache of capacity W representing the knapsack and there is one user u (of weight 1) adjacent to this cache such that $p_{u s_i} := v_i / \sum_{i=1}^n v_i$ for all $i \in [n]$. Set $\ell := t / \sum_{i=1}^n v_i$. This completes the construction of (G, ℓ) , which is clearly achieved in polynomial time.

By observing that the values of the items and t have been normalized so that their corresponding request probabilities and ℓ , respectively, are in the range $[0, 1]$, the equivalence of the two instances is immediate. Indeed, storing a content in the cache corresponds to placing its corresponding item in the knapsack as the size and request probabilities of the contents correspond to the weights and (relative) values of the items, respectively, the cache and the knapsack have the same capacity, and thus, a cache hit rate of at least ℓ is achieved if and only if there is a subset of the items of total value at least t that can be placed in the knapsack. \square

A straightforward corollary of the proof of Theorem 10 yields that HETNC-B is NP-hard, even if there is only one cache and each user requests a single content.

Corollary 11. *HETNC-B is NP-hard, even if $C = \lambda = 1$.*

Proof. Let $s_1, \dots, s_{|I|}$ be the contents requested with probabilities $p_{u s_1}, \dots, p_{u s_{|I|}}$, respectively, by the single user u in the reduction in the proof of Theorem 10 (recall that $|I|$ is the number of items in the input instance of 0-1 KNAPSACK). We adapt that reduction as follows: instead of creating the user u , for each $s \in s_1, \dots, s_{|I|}$, we create a separate user u_s of weight $p_{u s}$. Each such user u_s only requests the content s , specifically with probability $p_{u_s s} = 1$, and is adjacent to the only cache in the instance. We set $\ell := t / \sum_{i=1}^n v_i$ as above.

To establish correctness, we again observe that our construction maintains a direct correspondence between storing

a content in a cache and placing the corresponding item in the knapsack. Hence, a caching allocation achieves a cache hit rate of $\ell := t / \sum_{i=1}^n v_i$ if and only if a subset of the items of total value at least t can be placed in the knapsack. \square

For some parameterizations, our results do not resolve whether they are FPT or W[1]-hard. In the final technical Section 6, we show that these open cases are interreducible.

5 Structural Parameters

In this section, we discuss an alternative approach towards identifying tractable fragments of HOMNC, specifically by exploiting well-established structural properties of the network. As we have seen, HETNC-B is NP-hard even if the network consists of a single edge, and HETNC-U is NP-hard even in star networks. Thus, they both remain paraNP-hard when parameterized by not only the fundamental structural parameter treewidth (Robertson and Seymour, 1986), but also by essentially all other established graph parameters including, e.g., treedepth (Nesetril and de Mendez, 2012), the feedback edge number (Ganian and Korchemna, 2021; Bredereck et al., 2022), and the vertex cover number (Bodlaender et al., 2023; Chalopin et al., 2024). Moreover, this implies that both problems remain NP-hard on planar networks—a property which is particularly relevant in the studied setting (see also Section 1). However, none of the hardness results presented thus far rule out tractability for HOMNC with respect to these structural parameters or planarity. As our next result, we show that most established structural parameters like treewidth, treedepth, and feedback edge number, as well as planarity, do not help even when dealing with the simpler homogeneous setting. We achieve this via a reduction from the following problem.

MAXIMUM k -VERTEX COVER

Input: A graph G and two positive integers k and t .

Question: Is there a subset of vertices $V' \subseteq V(G)$ such that $|V'| \leq k$ and at least t edges in G contain a vertex from V' ?

Theorem 12. *HOMNC is NP-hard even if $\lambda = 2$ and G is a star whose edges have each been subdivided once. Moreover, in this case it is also W[1]-hard parameterized by K .*

Proof. We reduce from MAXIMUM k -VERTEX COVER. From an instance (G, k, t) of MAXIMUM k -VERTEX COVER, we construct an instance (G', ℓ) of HOMNC as follows. For each edge $xy \in E(G)$, there is a user u_{xy}

Figure 3: Illustration of the subdivided star G' constructed in the proof of Theorem 12, where ab , aq , and xy are edges in the graph G from the instance of MAXIMUM k -VERTEX COVER.

(of weight 1) in G' that only requests (with non-zero probability) the contents x and y with equal probability (i.e., $p_{u_{xy}x} = p_{u_{xy}y} = 0.5$), and a cache c_{xy} of capacity 1 that is adjacent only to u_{xy} . There is also one cache c of capacity k that is adjacent to every user in G' . Lastly, set $\ell := (U+t)/2$. This completes the construction of (G', ℓ) , which is clearly achieved in polynomial time. Further, it is easy to verify that, in (G', ℓ) , $\lambda = 2$, $K = k$, and G' is a star whose edges have each been subdivided exactly once. See Figure 3 for an illustration of G' .

For the first direction, assume that there is a subset of vertices $V' \subseteq V(G)$ such that $|V'| \leq k$ and at least t edges in G contain a vertex from V' . For each vertex $v \in V'$, store the content v in the cache c in G' . For each edge $xy \in E(G)$ that contains exactly one vertex from V' , say x , store the content y in the cache c_{xy} . For the rest of the caches of the form c_{xy} , cache either the content x or the content y . Then, this is a feasible caching allocation in G' that ensures that at least t users have both of their contents (that they requested with non-zero probability) stored in adjacent caches, and the remaining at most $U-t$ users have exactly one of their contents (that they requested with non-zero probability) stored in an adjacent cache. Thus, this feasible caching allocation in G' achieves a cache hit rate of $t + (U-t)/2 = (U+t)/2 = \ell$.

For the other direction, assume that there is a feasible caching allocation in G' achieving a cache hit rate of ℓ . Initially, set $V' := \emptyset$. For each content v stored in the cache c by this caching allocation, add the vertex v to V' . Then, V' contains at most k vertices. Since this caching allocation in G' achieves a cache hit rate of ℓ , there are at least t users in G' for which both of the contents that they requested with non-zero probability are stored in adjacent caches. In particular, at least one of the contents they requested with non-zero probability is stored in the cache c . Since each of those users in G' corresponds to an edge in G containing both of the vertices that correspond to the contents requested with non-zero probability by that user, the set V' satisfies the desired property in G . That is, $|V'| \leq k$ and at least t edges in G contain a vertex from V' . \square

The previous theorem rules out tractability even on planar

networks, but does not do so when Δ and K are constants. In our next result, we rule out tractability for HOMNC, even when restricted to planar networks where Δ , λ , and K are all fixed constants. We establish this via a reduction from the NP-hard PLANAR 3-SAT-E3 problem (Middendorf and Pfeiffer, 1993), whose definition is as follows.

PLANAR 3-SAT-E3

Input: A 3-CNF formula ϕ in which each clause contains 2 or 3 literals, each variable appears in exactly 3 clauses, and its incidence graph is planar.

Question: Is there a satisfying assignment for ϕ ?

Theorem 13. HOMNC is NP-hard, even if G is planar, $K = 1$, $\lambda = 3$, and $\Delta = 5$.

Proof. We reduce from PLANAR 3-SAT-E3. From an instance ϕ of PLANAR 3-SAT-E3, we construct an instance (G, ℓ) of HOMNC as follows. Let x_1, \dots, x_n and C_1, \dots, C_m be the variables and clauses in ϕ , respectively. For each of the literals $x_1, \bar{x}_1, \dots, x_n, \bar{x}_n$ in ϕ , there is a content in the catalog with the same name. We construct G from the planar incidence graph G_ϕ of ϕ as follows. Each variable vertex x_i , $i \in [n]$, in G_ϕ corresponds to a cache c_{x_i} of capacity 1 in G . Each clause vertex C_j , $j \in [m]$, in G_ϕ corresponds to a user u_{C_j} (of weight 1) in G that only requests (with non-zero probability) the contents corresponding to the literals that the clause C_j contains, and u_{C_j} requests these contents with equal probability. Thus, if a variable appears in a clause in ϕ , then the variable's corresponding cache is adjacent to the clause's corresponding user in G . Further, for each cache c_{x_i} , $i \in [n]$, there is an additional cache c'_{x_i} and two additional users u_{x_i} and $u_{\bar{x}_i}$. The user u_{x_i} ($u_{\bar{x}_i}$, respectively) only requests the content x_i (\bar{x}_i , respectively) with non-zero probability, i.e., $p_{u_{x_i}x_i} = 1$ ($p_{u_{\bar{x}_i}\bar{x}_i} = 1$, respectively). Both the caches c_{x_i} and c'_{x_i} are adjacent to both the users u_{x_i} and $u_{\bar{x}_i}$. Since these are all the adjacencies of the cache c'_{x_i} and the users u_{x_i} and $u_{\bar{x}_i}$, their respective vertices can be placed arbitrarily close to c_{x_i} , thus maintaining that G is planar. Also, for each user u_{C_j} , $j \in [m]$, such that C_j contains three literals in ϕ , there are two additional caches $c_{u_{C_j}}$ and $c'_{u_{C_j}}$ of capacity 1 that are adjacent only to u_{C_j} . For each user u_{C_j} , $j \in [m]$, such that C_j contains only two literals in ϕ , there is one additional cache $c_{u_{C_j}}$ of capacity 1 that is adjacent only to u_{C_j} . Similarly, these are all the adjacencies of these additional caches, and so, their respective vertices can be placed arbitrarily close to u_{C_j} , thus maintaining that G is planar. Lastly, set $\ell := U$. This completes the construction of (G, ℓ) , which is clearly achieved in polynomial time. Further, it is easy to verify that, in (G, ℓ) , G is planar, $K = 1$, $\lambda = 3$, and $\Delta = 5$ (since each variable appears in 3 clauses in ϕ). See Figure 4 for an illustration of G .

Figure 4: Illustration of the planar graph G constructed from an instance ϕ of PLANAR 3-SAT-E3 in the proof of Theorem 13. Here, ϕ contains the clause C_1 containing the variables x_1, x_2 , and a third arbitrary one (denoted by a line protruding from the vertex u_{C_1}), the clause C_2 containing the variables x_1, x_2 , and x_n , and the clause C_m containing the variables x_1, x_n , and a third arbitrary one.

For the first direction, assume that there is a satisfying assignment for ϕ . For each $i \in [n]$, if the satisfying assignment for ϕ sets the variable x_i to True (False, respectively), then store the content x_i (\bar{x}_i , respectively) in the cache c_{x_i} in G . For each $i \in [n]$, if the content stored in the cache c_{x_i} according to the above caching allocation is x_i (\bar{x}_i , respectively), then store the content \bar{x}_i (x_i , respectively) in the cache c'_{x_i} in G . Then, the current caching allocation in G ensures that, for all $i \in [n]$, the user u_{x_i} ($u_{\bar{x}_i}$, respectively) is adjacent to a cache that stored the content x_i (\bar{x}_i , respectively). Further, since this caching allocation corresponds to a satisfying assignment for ϕ , it ensures that, for all $j \in [m]$, the user u_{C_j} is adjacent to a cache that stored one of the contents corresponding to one of the literals that the clause C_j contains in ϕ . Indeed, each clause C_j , $j \in [m]$, in ϕ corresponds to a user u_{C_j} in G that is adjacent to 2 or 3 caches that correspond to the 2 or 3 variables contained in C_j in ϕ . To complete the caching allocation, for each $j \in [m]$, for the at most 2 remaining contents (at most 1 if C_j contains only two literals in ϕ) requested with non-zero probability by the user u_{C_j} that may not already be stored in one of its adjacent caches of the form c_{x_i} , it suffices to store one of them in the cache $c_{u_{C_j}}$ and the other in the cache $c'_{u_{C_j}}$ (if it exists and if needed). Thus, this caching allocation in G achieves a cache hit rate of ℓ , and it is easy to check that it is feasible.

For the other direction, assume that there is a feasible caching allocation in G achieving a cache hit rate of ℓ . Since it achieves a cache hit rate of ℓ , this caching allocation ensures that, for each $i \in [n]$, the cache c_{x_i} stored either the content x_i or the content \bar{x}_i since $p_{u_{x_i}x_i} = 1$ and $p_{u_{\bar{x}_i}\bar{x}_i} = 1$, and the users u_{x_i} and $u_{\bar{x}_i}$ are only adjacent to one other

cache of capacity 1, namely c'_{x_i} . For each $i \in [n]$, if this caching allocation in G stores the content x_i (\bar{x}_i , respectively) in the cache c_{x_i} , then set the variable x_i to True (False, respectively). We now argue that this results in a satisfying assignment for ϕ . Recall that, for each $j \in [m]$, the user u_{C_j} either has 1 (if C_j contains only two literals in ϕ) or 2 (if C_j contains three literals in ϕ) additional caches adjacent to it that are not of the form c_{x_i} . Hence, this caching allocation ensures that, for each $j \in [m]$, one of the contents requested with non-zero probability by the user u_{C_j} is stored in a cache of the form c_{x_i} adjacent to u_{C_j} . As each of these contents corresponds to one of the literals contained in the clause C_j in ϕ , the above truth assignment for ϕ is a satisfying one. \square

Neither of the previous results rules out tractability for HOMNC when parameterized by the vertex cover number of the graph, which is the minimum size of a subset S of the vertices such that every edge is incident to at least one vertex in S . In the next section dedicated to unifying the remaining open cases, we show that, for HOMNC, this parameterization is complexity-theoretically equivalent to several other ones we already considered. As a by-product, this yields XP-tractability for HOMNC parameterized by the vertex cover number, contrasting the lower bounds ruling out the use of essentially all other structural graph parameters.

6 Interreducibility: Linking the Open Cases

For several of the studied cases, we obtained XP algorithms, but lack the corresponding W[1]-hardness proofs which would rule out inclusion in FPT. In this section, for all parameterizations of HOMNC which we show to admit XP algorithms in Section 3 (in particular C , U , $C + U$, $C + \lambda$, and $U + K$) and also for the vertex cover number parameter mentioned at the end of the previous section, we prove the following: either HOMNC is W[1]-hard for each of these, or it is FPT for each of these. That is, all of the arising parameterized problems are equivalent and there is only a single open case left for HOMNC. We emphasize that these results are not trivial, as here it does not hold that bounding one parameter is immediately equivalent to bounding the other.

Theorem 14. *Let \varkappa and \varkappa' denote any two of the following six parameters: C , U , $U + K$, $C + U$, $C + \lambda$, and the vertex cover number $\text{vc}(G)$. Then, there exists a parameterized reduction from HOMNC parameterized by \varkappa to HOMNC parameterized by \varkappa' .*

Proof. First, note that we do not need to present parameterized reductions in the cases where $\varkappa \geq \varkappa'$ as the trivial reduction where the two instances are identical is valid in

these cases. In particular, this implies that we do not need to consider the case where $\varkappa = C + U$ and $\varkappa' = \text{vc}(G)$. We now provide a case analysis that can easily be checked to be exhaustive as parameterized reductions respect transitivity. Also, since each of the following reductions takes polynomial time and the equivalence of the two instances is immediate, we simply present the reductions.

Case 1: $\varkappa = U$ and $\varkappa' = C$. This case was covered in the proof of Observation 5.

Case 2: $\varkappa = C$ and $\varkappa' = U$. From an instance (G, ℓ) of HOMNC with C caches, we obtain an equivalent instance (G', ℓ) of HOMNC with $U' \leq 2^C$ users as follows. For each set $U^* \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ of 2 or more users with the same neighborhood in G , delete all the users except for one, denote this user by u^* , and set the weight and content request probabilities of u^* in such a way that any potential cache hits for U^* in G would result in the same amount of cache hits for u^* in G' . Specifically, $w(u^*) := \sum_{u \in U^*} w(u)$ and $p_{u^*s} := (\sum_{u \in U^*} w(u)p_{us}) / w(u^*)$ for each $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Since there are 2^C different subsets of the caches in G , there are at most 2^C users in G' .

Case 3: $\varkappa = U$ and $\varkappa' = U + K$. From an instance (G, ℓ) of HOMNC with U users, we obtain an equivalent instance (G', ℓ) of HOMNC with a maximum cache capacity of $K' = 1$ and U users as follows. Let C be the number of caches in (G, ℓ) . For each $i \in [C]$, replace the cache c_i in G by $\kappa(c_i)$ caches of capacity 1 (recall that $\kappa(c_i) \leq S$) with the same neighborhood as c_i .

Case 4: $\varkappa = C$ and $\varkappa' = C + \lambda$. From an instance (G, ℓ) of HOMNC with C caches, we obtain an equivalent instance (G', ℓ) of HOMNC with C caches in which each user requests only a single content with probability 1 as follows. For each user u in G , delete u , and, for each content s requested with non-zero probability by u , add a user u_s with weight $w(u) \cdot p_{us}$ such that $p_{u_s s} = 1$ and u_s has the same neighborhood as u had.

Case 5: $\varkappa = \text{vc}(G)$ and $\varkappa' = C + U$. From an instance (G, ℓ) of HOMNC with vertex cover number $\text{vc}(G)$, we obtain an equivalent instance (G', ℓ) of HOMNC where the number of caches and users are both upper-bounded by $\text{vc}(G)$ as follows. Let C and U be the number of caches and users in (G, ℓ) , respectively, and let \mathcal{U} be the set of users in (G, ℓ) . We first use the simple polynomial-time 2-approximation algorithm for VERTEX COVER to compute a vertex cover X of G such that $X \leq 2 \cdot \text{vc}(G)$, and let $I = V(G) \setminus X$. By the definition of X , I is an independent set. For each set $U^* \subseteq \mathcal{U} \cap I$ of 2 or more users with the same neighborhood in G , delete all the users except for one, denote this user by u^* , and set the weight and content request probabilities of u^* as in Case 2. For each set of 2 or more caches in I with the same neighborhood in G , delete all the caches except for one, and give this cache a capacity equal to the sum of the capacities of those deleted caches plus its original ca-

capacity. As there are at most $2^{|X|}$ distinct subsets of users and caches in X , there are at most $2^{|X|+|X|} \leq 4^{\text{vc}(G)} + 2 \cdot \text{vc}(G)$ caches and users in G' . \square

We conjecture that HOMNC is W[1]-hard under these parameterizations, but believe that a proof requires novel techniques or insights into the problem. Moreover, as HETNC-U generalizes HOMNC, resolving this conjecture in the affirmative would also resolve the sole open case for HETNC-U.

7 Generalizations, Impact, and Conclusion

The FPT algorithms developed in Theorems 1 and 3 can be easily adapted to handle a more general framework associated with NETWORK-CACHING since they consider all the relevant feasible caching allocations. Indeed, for any objective function that can be computed in the desired FPT time when given a caching allocation, these algorithms can also compute the optimal value of that objective function along with its associated caching allocation. Moreover, most objective functions in the literature satisfy the above condition. For example, these algorithms can be trivially modified to deal with variants of NETWORK-CACHING where weights are added to the edges of the bipartite graph which represent the caching gain obtained from retrieving a content requested by the user from a specific cache (Ioannidis and Yeh, 2016; Tsigkari and Spyropoulos, 2022), and/or the objective function concerns other metrics such as QoS, streaming rate or energy consumption (Paschos et al., 2020). Our hardness results also carry over to these variants as well as generalizations combining caching with other network-related decisions (Dehghan et al., 2016; Krolikowski et al., 2018; Ricardo et al., 2021). On the other hand, these hardness results cannot be lifted to non-discrete variants of NETWORK-CACHING, as these can typically be solved in polynomial time (Shanmugam et al., 2013).

All of our algorithms are deterministic and implementable in CDNs or inference delivery networks, and in fact it is reasonable to expect some of the studied parameters to achieve small values in practice (see also Section 2). However, we believe that a natural next step would be to find the theoretically fastest algorithms under the (Strong) Exponential Time Hypothesis. Further, designing informed heuristics based on our complexity analysis—as was successfully done in other fields (Bäckström et al., 2012; Rost et al., 2019; Komusiewicz et al., 2023)—would be an interesting alternate direction one could take.

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